

1 Thermotopes-COH — a software for carbon isotope modeling and
2 speciation of COH fluids

3

4 Antoine Boutier^{1,2,3*}, Isabelle Martinez³, Isabelle Daniel², Simone Tumiati⁴, Guillaume Siron⁵,
5 Alberto Vitale Brovarone^{5,6,7}

6 ¹*Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Università degli Studi di Torino, Via Valperga Caluso 35,*
7 *10100 Torino, Italy, ORCID: 0000-0003-4013-0566*

8 ²*Université de Lyon, Univ Lyon 1, ENS de Lyon, CNRS UMR 5276, LGL-TPE, Villeurbanne*
9 *Cedex, France*

10 ³*Université Paris Cité, Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris, CNRS, UMR 7154, F-75005, Paris,*
11 *France.*

12 ⁴*Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Università degli Studi di Milano, via Mangiagalli 34, I-*
13 *20133, Milano, Italy*

14 ⁵*Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche e Ambientali, Via Zamboni, 67, Bologna, Italy*

15 ⁶*Institut de Minéralogie, de Physique des Matériaux et de Cosmochimie (IMPMC), Sorbonne*
16 *Université, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, UMR CNRS 7590, IRD UR206, 75005 Paris,*
17 *France*

18 ⁷*Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources, National Research Council of Italy, Pisa, Italy*

19 *Corresponding authors: antoine.boutier@gmail.com; alberto.vitaleb@unibo.it

20 Authorship Statement:
21 Category 1:
22 Conception and design of study: Antoine Boutier, Alberto Vitale Brovarone
23 Coding: Antoine Boutier
24 Concept and features consultation: Simone Tumiati, Guillaume Siron.
25 Category 2:
26 Drafting the manuscript: Antoine Boutier, Alberto Vitale Brovarone.
27 Revising the manuscript critically for important intellectual content: Isabelle Martinez,
28 Isabelle Daniel, Simone Tumiati, Guillaume Siron.
29 Category 3:
30 Approval of the version of the manuscript to be published: Antoine Boutier, Alberto Vitale
31 Brovarone, Isabelle Martinez, Isabelle Daniel, Simone Tumiati, Guillaume Siron.
32
33

34 Abstract

35 Carbon-bearing fluids and condensed carbon are common on and inside planetary bodies.
36 Understanding the mechanisms capable of transferring carbon from fluids into solids and
37 vice-versa is central in many fundamental and applied research targets within the Earth and
38 Planetary Sciences. A broad range of applications can benefit from the thermodynamic
39 properties of carbon-oxygen-hydrogen (COH) systems. As an example, the precipitation of
40 natural graphite or diamond can be modeled within the COH thermodynamic systems.
41 Because the evolution of COH fluids implies isotopic fractionation among different species,
42 carbon stable isotopes can be used in conjunction with thermodynamic calculations to
43 reconstruct graphite or diamond formation mechanisms, or the evolution of fluid species such
44 as carbon dioxide or methane.

45 Thermotopes-COH is a Python-based graphical user interface (GUI) software for computation
46 of thermodynamic and carbon isotopic modeling in the C-O-H system within the 0.1 – 5 GPa
47 and 300 – 900 °C range. The software allows generic and process-oriented thermodynamic
48 and carbon stable isotope calculations including fluid mixing, fluid-graphite/diamond
49 interactions with changing pressure or temperature, and fluid desiccation. This versatile
50 numerical tool is designed to model processes of dissolution/precipitation of graphite or
51 diamond. Along with a description of the software functions, this contribution also provides
52 practical examples.

53 Keywords: Carbon, Isotopes, COH-fluid, Modeling, Thermodynamics

54 1 Introduction

55 Carbon cycling on Earth is pivotal in bridging biological and geological processes, energy fluxes
56 in both shallow and deep environments, and climatic and global environmental changes
57 (Berner, 1999; Dasgupta, 2013; Dasgupta and Hirschmann, 2010; Evans, 2011). Carbon is
58 ubiquitous in geologic fluids, e.g., in hydrocarbon-rich fluids, as small fractions in aqueous
59 fluids or dominant in CO₂-rich systems (Connolly and Cesare, 1993; Huang et al., 2017; Kokh
60 et al., 2017). Carbon isotope geochemistry has long been used to track sources and processes
61 in geologic systems (Baumgartner and Valley, 2001; Bebout and Fogel, 1992; Duke and
62 Rumble, 1986; Kitchen and Valley, 1995; Luque et al., 2012; Mason et al., 2017; Ray, 2009;
63 Ray and Ramesh, 2000; Stachel et al., 2017; Tumiati et al., 2022; Valley, 1986).

64 Carbon also is a redox-sensitive element, and its isotopic evolution strongly depends on the
65 thermodynamic evolution of the geologic system under consideration. The COH
66 thermodynamic system has long been used to model the evolution of many geological fluids
67 and fluid-rock systems as a function of pressure (P), temperature (T), and redox state. Some
68 examples include the study of graphite or diamond precipitation from carbon-
69 saturated/supersaturated fluids, graphite dissolution in response to regional metamorphism
70 or fluid infiltration, and the subsequent speciation in fluid inclusions (Cesare, 1995; Connolly,
71 1995; Connolly and Cesare, 1993; French, 1966; Ohmoto and Kerrick, 1977; Taylor and Liou,
72 1978; Taylor and Green, 1986; Ulmer and Luth, 1991; Huizenga 2005; Galvez et al., 2013;
73 Vitale Brovarone et al., 2020).

74 The thermodynamics of the COH system has also been used to reconstruct the carbon isotopic
75 evolution of graphite or diamond precipitation at carbon saturation conditions (Duke and
76 Rumble, 1986; Stachel et al., 2017; Ortega et al., 2010; Boutier et al., 2023). While the

77 relations governing the chemical equilibria of the COH system and its isotopes exist (Duke and
78 Rumble, 1986, Holloway, 1984; Huizenga, 2005; Spycher and Reed, 1988; Rumble and
79 Hoering, 1986), their integration into a single, user-friendly software is not yet available.
80 Furthermore, when complex fluid or fluid/rock evolutions are considered within the COH
81 system, the isotopic trend of the resulting fluid and solid phases may be challenging to model
82 or even counterintuitive (Stachel et al., 2017).

83 Although numerical tools allowing computation of simple isotope equilibria exist (e.g.,
84 Beaudoin and Therrien, 2009, 2004), the computations are often done using user-made,
85 specific spreadsheets. The Thermotopes-COH software integrates carbon isotope and
86 thermodynamic models allowing for complex fluid and fluid-rock reactions and interactions
87 within the COH chemical system. It features multiple functions through five interactive tabs:
88 (1) carbon isotopic equilibrium, (2) carbon isotopic fractionation modeling, (3) multi-
89 component solid-C precipitation, (4) COH fluid speciation, and (5) graphite/diamond
90 dissolution/precipitation. The core of Thermotopes-COH provides advanced tools to model
91 the thermodynamic and isotopic evolution of fluids and their interactions with
92 graphite/diamond-bearing rocks within the COH chemical system. The software offers generic
93 and process-oriented modeling options spanning the most common mechanisms of
94 graphite/diamond precipitation or dissolution and a fast graphical visualization of the
95 modeling results. The software also offers the possibility to perform conventional calculations
96 such as carbon isotopic equilibria and fractionation modeling for further use as internal input
97 parameters for the more advanced options.

98 This Python-based software runs on Windows and MacOS. It is a standalone executable that
99 does not require any additional installation of packages. The software and documentation are

100 available at <https://zenodo.org/record/8364254>. This contribution presents the software
101 functions and principles, as well as examples of applications of its functionalities.

102 2 Isotope and thermodynamic database

103 2.1 Isotope database

104 Isotope fractionation equations can be presented under various form, with the most
105 comprehensive as follow:

$$106 \quad \Delta = 1000 \ln \alpha = A \frac{(10^{3n})}{T^n} + \dots + D \frac{(10^6)}{T^2} + E \frac{(10^3)}{T} + F \quad (1)$$

107 where Δ is the isotopic fractionation, α is the fractionation factor, A to F are experimentally
108 determined parameters and T is temperature in K.

109 Since the higher order terms have been recognized to contribute insignificantly to isotopic
110 fractionation between two phases (Richet et al., 1977), the isotopic database of
111 Thermotopes-COH uses a simplified version of the general equation limited to the second
112 power:

$$113 \quad \Delta = 1000 \ln \alpha = A \frac{(10^6)}{T^2} + B \frac{(10^3)}{T} + C \quad (2)$$

114 This model includes a wide range of available references in the COH system but may limit the
115 implementation of additional fractionation factors containing higher order terms. The full list
116 of fractionation factors featured in the carbon isotopic database used in Thermotopes-COH is
117 presented in Table 1.

118

119

120 Table 1: List of fractionation factor available in Thermotopes-COH

Isotopic Couple	Temperature range	Reference
CO ₂ -CH ₄	0-700°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Graphite-CH ₄	0-700°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Calcite-CH ₄	0-700°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Calcite-Aragonite	25°C	Rubinson, M. and Clayton, R.N. (1969)
Diamond-Graphite	0-1000°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Calcite-CO ₂	100-700°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
		Bottinga, Y. (1968)
	0-100°C	Deines, P.; Langmuir, D.; and Harmon, R.S. (1974)
	900°C	Rosenbaum, J.M. (1994)
	0-600°C	Ohmoto, H.; and Rye, R.O. (1979)
Calcite-Graphite	0-700°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
	400-800°C	Dunn, S.R. and Valley, J.W. (1992)
	400-680°C	Wada, H. & Suzuki, K. (1983)
	600-1200°C	Scheele, N. & Hoefs, J. (1992)
	700-800°C	Kitchen, N.E. & Valley, J.W. (1995)
	600-1400°C	Deines, P., Eggler, D.H. (2009)
CO ₂ -Graphite	100-700°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
	0-1000°C	Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Diamond-CO ₂		Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Diamond-CH ₄		Bottinga, Y. (1969)
Dolomite-CO ₂		Ohmoto, H.; and Rye, R.O. (1979)
Calcite-HCO ₃	0-100 °C	Deines, P. et al. (1974)
CO-CO ₂	0-330 °C	Ohmoto, H. & Rye, R.O. (1979)

122 2.2 Thermodynamic database

123 The thermodynamic calculations in the Thermotopes-COH software follow the COH model by
124 Huizenga (2005) based on the numerous equations of state available allowing a wide range
125 of initial input parameters. The thermodynamic data for solids are taken from Shi and Saxena
126 (1992). The list of considered oxygen fugacity buffers is presented in Table 2. The
127 thermodynamic dataset for diamond/graphite is from Day (2012).

128 Table 2: List of oxygen fugacity buffers available in Thermotopes-COH

Oxygen fugacity buffer	Reference
FMQ <i>(Fayalite-Magnetite-Quartz)</i>	Miozzi & Tumiati (2020) O'Neill (1987) and Ballhaus et al. (1991) Ohmoto & Kerrick (1977)
Hem-Mag <i>(Hematite-Magnetite)</i>	Ballhaus et al. (1991) Frost (1991)
Fe-Wus <i>(Iron-Wustite)</i>	Ballhaus et al. (1991) Frost (1991)
Ni-NiO	Ballhaus et al. (1991) Frost (1991)
EMOD <i>(Enstatite-Magnesite-Olivine-Diamond/Graphite)</i>	Stagno and Frost (2010)

129

130

131 3 Thermotopes-COH structure and functions

132

133 This section presents the modeling functions of Thermotopes-COH, their assumptions, and
134 some practical examples. The Thermotopes-COH GUI displays five different tabs. The first
135 three tabs are designed to obtain input parameters for the following ones. The tabs called
136 “Isotopic equilibrium” and “Isotopic fractionation”, respectively, provide isotopic input
137 parameters at desired conditions, including simple isotope equilibria and open/closed system
138 isotope fractionation. The third tab, called “Multicomponent solid-C” provides a first coupling
139 of COH thermodynamics and isotope evolution for multi-component, carbon-saturated
140 systems. The fourth tab, called “COH system” is centered on the thermodynamics of the COH
141 system and provides carbon isotope evolution for fluid and solid species. The fifth tab, called
142 “Dissolution/precipitation”, provides process-oriented integration of thermodynamic and
143 isotope evolutions of fluid species and condensed carbon minerals (graphite/diamond).

144 3.1 Isotopic equilibrium

145 The tab labeled “Isotopic equilibrium” is the basic building block of Thermotopes-COH. It
146 calculates isotopic equilibrium between two carbon-bearing species, using the following
147 expression:

$$148 \delta_A = \delta_B + \Delta_{A-B} \quad (3)$$

149 where δ_A is the isotopic composition of A in per mille (‰), δ_B is the isotopic composition of
150 B in permil (‰), Δ_{A-B} is the isotopic shift between A and B calculated after Eq.(2) (Kendall
151 and McDonnell, 2012; Sharp, 2017). The list of isotopic couples available in this tab is shown
152 in Table 1.

153 3.2 Isotopic fractionation

154 The tab labeled “Isotopic fractionation” calculates batch or Rayleigh fractionation evolutions
155 of a C-bearing species. Isotopic fractionation between species A to B is calculated at
156 equilibrium. Batch (or closed system) fractionation is derived from mass balance equation
157 (Valley, 1986):

$$158 \delta_B^f = (\delta_A^{initial} - \Delta_{A-B}) \times (1 - f) + (\delta_A^{initial} \times f) \quad (4)$$

$$159 \delta_A^f = \delta_B^f + \Delta_{A-B} \quad (5)$$

160 Rayleigh (or open system) fractionation follows the so-called Rayleigh equation (Rayleigh,
161 1896):

$$162 \delta_A^f = ((1000 + \delta_A^{initial})f^{\alpha_{A-B}-1}) - 1000 \quad (6)$$

$$163 \delta_B^f = \frac{(1000 + \delta_A^f)}{\alpha_{A-B}} - 1000 \quad (7)$$

164 where f is the remaining fraction of A, $\delta_A^{initial}$ is the initial isotopic composition at the
165 beginning of the fractionation, δ_A^f and δ_B^f are the isotopic composition at f , and α_{A-B} is the
166 fractionation factor calculated after Eq.(2) (Dansgaard, 1964; Kendall and McDonnell, 2012;
167 Sharp, 2017; Valley, 1986).

168 Figure 1 shows two examples of modeling outputs for the isotope fractionation of graphite to
169 either CO₂ or CH₄ in closed or open system conditions, at 300 °C and 500 °C. This example
170 provides a quick visualization of the effect of temperature on the fractionation factor of the
171 graphite-CO₂ and graphite-CH₄ couples. It shows, for example, that the temperature effect is
172 more important for the graphite-CH₄ couple. This behavior has an important role in the
173 isotopic evolution of multi-component systems described in the next section.

174

175 Figure 1. Examples of closed (a, c) and open (b, d) system fractionation of graphite to either CO₂ (a, b) or CH₄ (c, d). Each panel shows fractionation evolution at 300 (solid line) and 500 °C (dashed line), respectively. The software allows to easily select a source and a product and to model their isotopic evolution as a function of the remaining fraction of the source at a given temperature. All species and fractionation factor available in the software are given in Table 1.

180 3.3 Multi-component graphite/diamond-CO₂-CH₄ modeling

181 The tab labeled “Multi-component solid-C” models the precipitation of either graphite or diamond, from a fluid containing both CO₂ and CH₄ according to the equation described successively by Ray (2009), Ray and Ramesh (2000), and by Stachel et al. (2017). The precipitation of graphite/diamond from a fluid containing both CO₂ and CH₄ follows two steps: initially, and as long as available, CO₂ and CH₄ contribute equally to the isotopic value of the resulting C_{solid} (0.5 mole each per mole of produced graphite/diamond). Then, when the less

187 abundant phase either CH₄ or CO₂ is totally consumed, precipitation evolves as a single
 188 component system following a classical Rayleigh model (see Tab 2). During the first step, the
 189 equations (12) and (17) defining the isotopic value of C_{solid} varies if the system is CH₄ or CO₂
 190 dominated (Ray, 2009; Ray and Ramesh, 2000; Stachel et al., 2017b). When CH₄ is more
 191 abundant than CO₂ the equations are:

$$192 \quad \delta^{13}C_{fluid}^f = 1000 \left(\frac{\alpha_{C-CH_4}}{A} \ln \frac{Af-B}{A-B} - \ln f \right) + \delta^{13}C_{fluid}^{initial} \quad (8)$$

$$193 \quad \delta^{13}C_{C\ solid}^f = 1000 \left(\frac{\alpha_{C-CH_4}}{A-\frac{B}{f}} - 1 \right) + \delta^{13}C_{fluid}^f \left(\frac{\alpha_{C-CH_4}}{A-\frac{B}{f}} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$194 \quad r = \frac{X_{CO_2}}{X_{CH_4}} \quad (10)$$

$$195 \quad A = \frac{1 + \alpha_{CO_2-CH_4}}{2} \quad (11)$$

$$196 \quad B = (1 - r) \frac{\alpha_{CO_2-CH_4} - 1}{2 + 2r} \quad (12)$$

197 When CO₂ is more abundant than CH₄:

$$198 \quad \delta^{13}C_{fluid}^f = 1000 \left(\frac{\alpha_{C-CO_2}}{A} \ln \frac{Af-B}{A-B} - \ln f \right) + \delta^{13}C_{fluid}^{initial} \quad (13)$$

$$199 \quad \delta^{13}C_{C\ solid}^f = 1000 \left(\frac{\alpha_{C-CO_2}}{A-\frac{B}{f}} - 1 \right) + \delta^{13}C_{fluid}^f \left(\frac{\alpha_{C-CO_2}}{A-\frac{B}{f}} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$200 \quad r = \frac{X_{CH_4}}{X_{CO_2}} \quad (15)$$

$$201 \quad A = \frac{1 + \frac{1}{\alpha_{CO_2-CH_4}}}{2} \quad (16)$$

$$202 \quad B = (1 - r) \frac{\alpha_{CO_2-CH_4}}{2 + 2r} \quad (17)$$

203 where $\delta^{13}C_{fluid}^{initial}$ is the initial isotopic composition of the fluid, $\delta^{13}C_{fluid}^f$ the isotopic
 204 composition of the fluid for a remaining fraction of fluid f , $\delta^{13}C_{C\ solid}^f$ is the composition of
 205 graphite/diamond at the remaining fraction of fluid f , $\alpha_{CO_2-CH_4}$ the fractionation factor

206 between CO₂ and CH₄, α_{C-CO_2} the fractionation factor between graphite/diamond and CO₂
207 and α_{C-CH_4} the fractionation factor between graphite/diamond and CH₄.

208 Multi-component isotope calculations are performed by selecting an option for the input of
209 $\delta^{13}C$ isotopic composition of the fluid, either “Total C”, “Fluid mixing”, “Known CH₄
210 composition” or “Known CO₂ composition”.

211 -Total C: The fluid is considered in internal isotopic equilibrium and the total $\delta^{13}C$ value of the
212 fluid is entered. The isotopic compositions of CO₂ and CH₄ are then calculated based on their
213 respective proportion at the desired temperature.

214 -Fluid mixing: Two fluids initially at isotopic disequilibrium contain either CO₂ or CH₄. Once
215 the precipitation starts, the two fluids mix to reach isotopic equilibrium and then ensue the
216 precipitation of graphite/diamond.

217 -Known CH₄ (or CO₂) composition: The fluid is at isotopic equilibrium but only the $\delta^{13}C$ CH₄ (or
218 CO₂) composition is known by the user. In this case, software will model the associated
219 missing $\delta^{13}C$ composition at the desired temperature and derives the precipitation of
220 graphite/diamond.

221 Please note that the modeling of graphite/diamond precipitation from the tab “Multi-
222 component G/D-C-O-H modeling” does not involve thermodynamic computations.
223 Nevertheless, the isotopic mass balance used for the multi-component modeling follows the
224 same principles of evolving COH speciation as those that define the thermodynamic modeling
225 presented in section 3.4.

226 Figure 2 shows two examples of multi-component graphite precipitation models for CH₄/CO₂
227 ratios >1 and <1, respectively, at 300 °C and 500 °C. The initial bulk δ¹³C is -5‰ in both cases.
228 The evolution of single component systems for either CH₄ or pure CO₂ is also shown for
229 comparison. As observed by Stachel et al. (2017), the evolution of multi-component systems
230 may result in counterintuitive trends. In Figure 2, it can be observed that, depending on the
231 initial CH₄/CO₂ ratio, the coexisting fluid and graphite follow consistent (CH₄/CO₂ ratio < 1) or
232 opposite trends (CH₄/CO₂ ratio > 1), because Δ_{graphite-CH₄} is smaller than Δ_{graphite-CO₂}. This results
233 in a progressive enrichment in ¹³C in the precipitating graphite and a progressive enrichment
234 in X_{CH₄} (and therefore a depletion in ¹³C in the remaining fluid) for fluid with CH₄/CO₂ ratio >
235 1, or a progressive enrichment in both ¹³C in the precipitating graphite and X_{CO₂} for fluid with
236 CH₄/CO₂ ratio < 1. Depending on the temperature conditions, the fluid and graphite isotopic
237 trends do or do not cross each other (Figure 2). This is the result of the multi-component
238 evolution, when the fluid and precipitating solid may transiently have the same δ¹³C
239 composition. Such a feature is generally observed for a complete transformation in a closed
240 reservoir (for example, full transformation of CO₂ to graphite), whereas in the present case it
241 is observed for transient open-system conditions. As introduced in the previous section, the
242 diversity in temperature dependence between the graphite-CO₂ and graphite-CH₄ couples
243 determines remarkable variations in the isotopic fractionation of the precipitating graphite,
244 especially for CH₄/CO₂ ratios >1. In particular, at 300 °C for a CH₄/CO₂ ratio >1, the first
245 precipitating graphite is enriched in ¹³C relative to the fluid source, whereas at 500 °C the first
246 precipitating graphite is depleted in ¹³C relative to the fluid source. This is due to the
247 difference between Δ_{graphite-CH₄} and Δ_{graphite-CO₂} that decreases with increasing temperature. In
248 other words, Δ_{CH₄-CO₂} decreases with increasing temperature but with more substantial
249 variations for the CH₄-graphite pair. Although Δ_{graphite-CH₄} remains smaller than Δ_{graphite-CO₂} with

250 increasing temperature, the decreasing $\Delta_{\text{CH}_4\text{-CO}_2}$ with increasing temperature determines, for
 251 a fixed CH_4/CO_2 ratio > 1 , that the first precipitating graphite is enriched in ^{13}C relative to the
 252 fluid source at low temperature, whereas it is depleted in ^{13}C relative to the fluid source at
 253 higher temperature. The successive fractionation trends are controlled by the evolving
 254 CH_4/CO_2 ratio as described above.

255

256 Figure 2. Examples of multi-component isotope fractionation trends for $\text{CH}_4/\text{CO}_2 = 1.8$ (CH_4 0.64; CO_2 0.36) at 300
 257 °C (a) and 500 °C (b) and $\text{CH}_4/\text{CO}_2 = 0.4$ (CH_4 0.29; CO_2 0.71) at 300 °C (c) and 500 °C (d), for initial $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -5$ ‰.
 258 Single component fractionations are also shown for reference. The system firstly evolves as multi-component
 259 (solid lines) until the less abundant molecule – CO_2 in (a,b), CH_4 in (c,d)– is exhausted. Secondly, it evolves as a
 260 single-component system (dashed lines).

261 3.4 COH fluid speciation

262 The tab labeled “COH system” models the speciation of COH fluids, the carbon activity, the
263 X_O , and the oxygen and hydrogen fugacities. The modeling follows equations from Huizenga
264 (2005) and references therein, and calculates the speciation of the COH fluid using the
265 following equilibria:

270 From these equilibria, the oxygen fugacity f_{O_2} along with the molar fractions of X_{H_2O} , X_{CO_2} ,
271 X_{CH_4} , X_{H_2} and X_{CO} , are calculated. X_O is defined as $X_O = \frac{n_O}{n_O + n_H}$ where n_O and n_H are the atomic
272 proportions of oxygen and hydrogen in the fluid, respectively (Connolly and Cesare, 1993).

273 The model assumes ideal mixing. Details of the equation for the equilibrium constants of
274 reaction and fugacity coefficients can be found in Huizenga (2005) and reference therein.

275 f_{H_2} is calculated according to the following equation (Holloway, 1977):

276 $f_{H_2} = \gamma_{H_2} \times P \times X_{H_2}$ (22)

277 Where X_{H_2} is the molar fraction of H_2 , P is the pressure in bar, and γ_{H_2} is the fugacity
278 coefficient of hydrogen calculated following Huizenga (2005). The carbon activity is the
279 effective concentration of carbon in the fluid. A carbon activity of 1 indicates that the fluid is
280 saturated in carbon and coexists with graphite/diamond. Carbon activity above to 1 refers to
281 a carbon oversaturated fluid or to the equilibrium with a non-ideal (e.g., disordered) carbon

282 form (Tumiati et al., 2020; Vitale Brovarone et al., 2020), which is not integrated in the current
283 version of the software. Carbon activity lower than one refers to graphite/diamond-
284 undersaturated conditions.

285 Several modeling options are available that require either 2 or 3 input parameters among:

- 286 ● known carbon activity, f_{O_2} buffer, and a $\Delta \log f_{O_2}$ from this buffer
- 287 ● known carbon activity and $X_{CO_2}/(X_{CO_2} + X_{CH_4})$ ratio. A f_{O_2} buffer can be indicated for
288 reference.
- 289 ● known $X_{CO_2}/(X_{CO_2} + X_{CH_4})$ ratio, f_{O_2} buffer, and a $\Delta \log f_{O_2}$ from this buffer
- 290 ● known carbon activity and X_O . A f_{O_2} buffer can be indicated for reference.
- 291 ● known $X_{CO_2}/(X_{CO_2} + X_{CH_4})$ ratio and X_{H_2O} . A f_{O_2} buffer can be indicated for reference.

292 The $\Delta \log f_{O_2}$ correspond to the relative difference to the selected oxygen fugacity buffer. For
293 example, for a fluid at $\Delta FMQ+1$ (log units), $\Delta \log f_{O_2}$ value is 1.

294 The results can be visualized on a ternary COH diagram (Fig. 3). The latter displays the location
295 of the carbon saturation curve and the position of the modeled COH fluid composition. The
296 software also allows expanding the computations over a pressure-temperature range and to
297 plot them on a P-T diagram (Fig. 4).

298

299

300 Figure 3. (a) Example of ternary COH diagram showing a generic carbon saturation curve separating the field of
 301 carbon-undersaturated fluids from the field where the fluid coexists with graphite/diamond. (b-d) Ternary COH
 302 diagrams showing the position of the carbon saturation curve for different temperatures and constant pressure
 303 (b), for different pressures at constant temperature (c), and along a prograde metamorphic path highlighting
 304 the positions of the FMQ buffer for four pressure-temperature couples (d). FMQ buffer from Miozzi and Tumati
 305 (2020).

306

307 Figure 4. (a) X_{O} colormap for a graphite saturated fluid at FMQ. (b) $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ colormap of a carbon-saturated fluid in
 308 equilibrium with graphite/diamond ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ graphite = -18 ‰), at FMQ. (c) $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ colormap of a carbon-saturated
 309 fluid in equilibrium with graphite/diamond ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ graphite = -18 ‰), at water-maximum conditions ($X_{\text{O}} = \frac{1}{3}$). (d)
 310 $\Delta\log\text{FMQ}$ colormap for a carbon-saturated fluid at water maximum ($X_{\text{O}} = \frac{1}{3}$).

311 3.4.1 Application to the study of carbon-saturated fluid inclusions

312 A potential application of the COH system tab is for the post entrapment fluid-component re-
 313 speciation in carbon-saturated fluid inclusions. Cesare (1995) described the transformation of
 314 graphite-saturated fluid inclusions during cooling and decompression. Provided that no mass
 315 is gained or lost by the inclusions, the original X_{O} ratio of the fluid phase should be constant
 316 (Cesare, 1995). Because the position of the carbon saturation curve within the COH diagram
 317 is dependent upon P and T conditions, cooling and/or decompression drive variations in f_{O_2}
 318 and carbon content of the fluid, which in turn leads to the precipitation of graphite inside the

319 inclusions. As a consequence, carbon speciation changes inside the fluid phase of the
320 inclusions. By compiling results for a series of P-T couples, Cesare (1995) concluded that the
321 $\text{CO}_2/(\text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4)$ ratio increases during cooling for fluids with initial $X_{\text{O}} > \frac{1}{3}$, whereas it
322 decreases for fluids with initial $X_{\text{O}} < \frac{1}{3}$. The P-T graph option of the COH system tab of
323 Thermotopes-COH offers the possibility to plot the $\text{CO}_2/(\text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4)$ ratio of graphite-
324 saturated fluids for constant X_{O} values and to assess the carbon speciation in the fluid along
325 any cooling and decompression path (Fig. 5). The $f\text{O}_2$ variation can also be plotted. If a fixed
326 composition for the initial graphite in equilibrium with the trapped fluid is set, the software
327 allows the calculation of P-T diagrams of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values for the bulk fluid, CH_4 , or CO_2 . Since these
328 diagrams assume a constant isotopic value for the graphite in equilibrium with the fluid
329 inclusion, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values across a P-T diagram generated through the COH tab do not take
330 into account any isotopic mass balance during the precipitation of graphite inside the
331 inclusions with decreasing pressure and temperature, which would induce isotopic
332 fractionation of the remaining fluid. For this reason, it is not recommended to use boldly the
333 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ results of the COH tab to track the isotopic evolution of fluid inclusions during pressure
334 and temperature variations unless the assumption is made that the solid carbon precipitated
335 inside the inclusion does reequilibrate isotopically after its formation. A way to overcome this
336 issue consists in considering a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ equal to 0‰ for the graphite coexisting with the fluid. This
337 way, the P-T diagrams for carbon isotopes represent directly the Δ between the fluid phases
338 (bulk, CO_2 , or CH_4) and the solid inside the inclusion.

339

340 Figure 5. Pressure-temperature diagrams for the carbon-saturated COH system. In (a) and (b), fixed X_0 values of
 341 0.3 and 0.38 are considered as representative of more reduced and more oxidized conditions, respectively,
 342 relative to the water-maximum conditions ($X_0 = \frac{1}{3}$). The ΔLogFMQ for both X_0 values is also shown in (c) and (d),
 343 respectively. Panels (e) and (f) show the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ evolution of the bulk fluid ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2$). As explained in the text, these
 344 values across the P-T space refer to a constant $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ for the solid carbon in equilibrium with the fluid. These
 345 diagrams were constructed for a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value of solid carbon at 0‰, so that, at any point within the diagram, the
 346 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value directly refers to the $\Delta\delta^{13}\text{C}$ between the solid and the bulk fluid.

347 3.5 Dissolution/precipitation of graphite/diamond

348 The tab labeled “Dissolution/precipitation”, offers process-oriented solutions to investigate
349 the precipitation and/or dissolution of graphite/diamond. The model assumes equilibrium
350 conditions and tracks the carbon activity of a COH-fluid through various reactions according
351 to the equations in Huizenga (2005). In short, graphite/diamond precipitation is obtained for
352 any fluid evolution resulting in carbon activity higher than 1, or when a carbon-saturated fluid
353 evolves along the carbon saturation curve from H₂O richer to H₂O poorer compositions.
354 Graphite/diamond dissolution is observed when the fluid evolves from carbon-saturated
355 conditions to carbon undersaturated conditions, or when a fluid evolves from H₂O poorer to
356 H₂O richer compositions along the carbon saturation curve. The governing equilibrium is:

358 The respective isotopic composition of the solid and fluid is calculated along the reaction path
359 according to reaction (23).

360 Since graphite/diamond may behave as a chemically reactive but isotopically inert phase
361 (Tumiati et al., 2022; Valley and O’Neil, 1981), an option is provided to allow
362 graphite/diamond to participate in the isotopic mass balance. When this option is toggled on,
363 the initial and newly formed graphite/diamond in the system can freely equilibrate with other
364 C-bearing species in the system and participate in the mass balance. The isotopic system is
365 considered to be closed, with carbon being either in the fluid phase or as graphite/diamond.
366 The composition of solid-C is calculated through the following equation:

$$367 \delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{solid}} = \delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{system}} - \frac{n_{\text{CO}_2}}{n_{\text{C}_{\text{total}}}} \Delta_{\text{CO}_2-\text{C}} - \frac{n_{\text{CH}_4}}{n_{\text{C}_{\text{total}}}} \Delta_{\text{CH}_4-\text{C}} \quad (24)$$

368 with $\delta^{13}C_{solid}$ being the isotopic composition of solid-C, $\delta^{13}C_{system}$ the isotopic composition
369 of the system, nCO_2 and nCH_4 the number of moles of CO_2 and CH_4 , respectively, nC_{total} the
370 total number of moles of carbon in the system Δ_{CO_2-C} and Δ_{CH_4-C} the isotopic capital delta
371 between CO_2 and graphite/diamond and CH_4 and graphite/diamond, respectively.

372 When this option is toggled off, graphite/diamond in the system does not participate in the
373 isotopic mass balance unless a fraction of this solid-C is dissolved. In this case, the isotopic
374 composition of the newly formed graphite/diamond is calculated considering the
375 instantaneous remaining fraction of carbon in the fluid f as follows:

$$376 \quad f = 1 - \left(\frac{nC_{solid\ new}}{nC_{H_4} + nC_{O_2}} \right) \quad (25)$$

377 The isotopic compositions of the instantaneous graphite/diamond and the total
378 graphite/diamond are then calculated from a combination of equation (4) and an isotopic
379 mass balance. A comparison of the isotopic calculation between the multicomponent system
380 and the Dissolution/precipitation model is presented in Supplementary material 1.

381 Thermotopes-COH offers six conceptual models for graphite/diamond
382 dissolution/precipitation, which are presented hereafter.

383 3.5.1 Dissolution/precipitation of graphite/diamond during fluid mixing

384 The fluid mixing process models the interaction of two different COH-fluids and their resulting
385 potential to dissolve or precipitate graphite/diamond. The software models the titration of
386 the second fluid into the first one through an iterative process. The titration step is defined
387 as 0.1% of the second fluid being mixed in the first one. The carbon activity of the fluid is
388 calculated and, if $a_c=1$, the titration proceeds to the next step. If the carbon activity is either
389 > 1 or < 1 , a sub-iteration starts with either dissolution or precipitation of graphite/diamond

390 until the carbon activity reaches 1. The associated isotopic evolution of fluid species and
391 graphite/diamond is computed at each step. The titration proceeds until the totality of the
392 second fluid is mixed within the first one.

393 Figure 6 shows examples of models involving the mixing of 100 moles of reduced graphite-
394 saturated fluid into 100 moles of a more oxidized one, at 500 °C and 1 GPa. The host fluid has
395 a $\text{CO}_2/(\text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4)$ ratio of 0.95, corresponding $f\text{O}_2$ values equivalent to the FMQ buffer, and
396 is in equilibrium with graphite with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -30 \text{ ‰}$, which corresponds to a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value of -20.6
397 for the fluid. The second fluid has a $\text{CO}_2/(\text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4)$ ratio of 1.9×10^{-4} , corresponding to
398 $\Delta\text{LogFMQ} = -3$, and is in equilibrium with graphite with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of -5 ‰, which corresponds to a
399 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of -34.9 ‰ for the fluid. Two examples are considered, with either inert or exchanging
400 graphite in the host system (1 mole graphite), respectively. The amount of graphite
401 precipitation, the $f\text{O}_2$ evolution, and the fluid component speciation are equivalent in both
402 cases, and characterized by the precipitation of about 31 moles of graphite, a decrease of the
403 $f\text{O}_2$ of about 3 log units, and by an increase of the $\text{CH}_4/(\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2)$ ratio from nearly 0 in the
404 host fluid, to about 1 in the mixed fluid. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the system, however, is different in the
405 two cases. The isotopic exchange of the host graphite (-30 ‰) results in a decrease of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$
406 of CO_2 and increase of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of CH_4 .

407

408 Figure 6. Examples of graphite precipitation through fluid mixing. Panel (a) shows the position of the two mixing
 409 fluids (both carbon-saturated) and the final one. Panel (b) shows the number of moles of graphite precipitated
 410 due to mixing. Panel (c) shows the evolution of the $\text{CH}_4/(\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2)$ ratio and XH_2O and (d) of the $f\text{O}_2$ during the
 411 mixing, respectively. Panels (e) and (f) show the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the solid, the bulk fluid, CO_2 , and CH_4 during the mixing
 412 for isotopically inert (e) and isotopically exchanging (f) initial solid. The mixing of 100 moles of fluid 1 with 100
 413 moles of fluid 2 was calculated at 500 °C, and for a preexisting graphite with $\delta^{13}\text{C} = -30\text{‰}$.

414 In these examples, it can be observed that the mixing of two carbon-saturated fluids may lead
415 to transient, counterintuitive trends in the carbon isotope evolution of both the fluid species
416 and the precipitated graphite. This includes isotopic values transiently heavier than the
417 heaviest fluid being involved in the mixing. This effect is due to the evolution of the mixing in
418 a complex multi-component ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{CH}_4$) system across the water-maximum: an initially CO_2 -
419 dominated fractionation trend, followed by a CH_4 -dominated one, and a contextual
420 precipitation of variable amounts of graphite during the mixing.

421 The software also offers the possibility to model fluid mixing at buffered f_{O_2} conditions. This
422 option models the interaction of a fluid with an f_{O_2} buffer, to simulate interaction in a
423 buffered medium. The f_{O_2} is $\Delta\log$ relative to a list of buffers (e.g., FMQ or EMOG), fixed during
424 the whole process, and the software models the composition of an external fluid equilibrating
425 with a constant f_{O_2} . If graphite/diamond precipitates, its isotopic composition is also
426 calculated. Geologically, buffering the f_{O_2} is not a trivial assumption and should be selected
427 only if consistent with the natural or experimental conditions.

428 3.5.2 Desiccation

429 This interaction models the evolution of a desiccating COH fluid (e.g., through rock hydration
430 reaction, or respeciation of H and O into C-bearing fluid species) and calculates the associated
431 precipitation of graphite/diamond. The desiccation is here defined as the loss of H_2O moles
432 from the initial fluid. In the desiccation mode, the oxygen fugacity is free to evolve during the
433 desiccation. During fluid desiccation, the carbon concentration increases and, if carbon
434 saturation is reached, graphite/diamond precipitates. The degree of desiccation that is
435 entered, corresponds to the fraction of the water loss ($X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$). The model is iterative and, at
436 each step, 0.01% of the moles of the initial H_2O ($n_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) is removed, the carbon activity is

437 calculated, and the number of moles of precipitated graphite/diamond and its isotopic value
 438 are derived. The calculation proceeds until the desired water fraction of the initial fluid is lost.
 439 Figure 7 shows desiccation of a fluid slightly oxidized relative to the water maximum at 600
 440 °C and 0.5 GPa ($\Delta\text{LogFMQ} = -0.5$, Fig. 7a) . The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the fluid was set at -10‰ , and the
 441 desiccation rate could proceed to 100%. Figure 7b shows that, during the desiccation of the
 442 chosen carbon-saturated COH fluid, graphite is constantly precipitated during a progressive
 443 increase in $f\text{O}_2$. Despite the desiccation ratio being set to 100%, the final fluid still contains
 444 some water (Fig. 7c). This water is produced in response to graphite/diamond precipitation
 445 and is not accounted for by the desiccation process. The newly formed water remains in the
 446 fluid. At the chosen high temperature conditions, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the precipitating graphite shows
 447 minimal variations during the desiccation process. As introduced in the previous section,
 448 lower temperatures should increase the range of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values in an evolving carbon-saturated
 449 COH fluid.

450

451 Figure 7. Desiccation model at 600 °C and 0.5 GPa. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the fluid was set at -10‰, and the f_{O_2} at ΔLogFMQ
452 = -0.5. Desiccation ratio was 100%. A: COH diagram showing the position of the fluid prior to the
453 interaction and its final position after graphite precipitation. B: Evolution of graphite
454 precipitation in response to changing f_{O_2} during desiccation. C: H_2O and $\text{CH}_4/(\text{CH}_4 + \text{CO}_2)$
455 proportions during desiccation. D: Isotopic composition of the fluid, of its C-bearing species
456 CO_2 and CH_4 , and of graphite formed in response to fluid desiccation.

457 Also, the desiccation option can be modeled at buffered f_{O_2} conditions. The desiccation is here
458 defined as the loss of H_2O mole in the fluid, and because the f_{O_2} is fixed during the interaction,
459 the water fraction in the fluid remains constant while the fluid stays at carbon saturation. In
460 other words, the actual amount of water decreases rather than its molar fraction. Any loss of
461 H_2O is accompanied by the loss of an equivalent amount of the other species in the fluid in
462 order to maintain $X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ constant. The amount of desiccation must be entered, because redox
463 conditions are buffered, $X_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ remains constant during desiccation. If graphite/diamond
464 precipitates, its isotopic composition is also calculated. Geologically speaking, buffering f_{O_2} is
465 not a trivial assumption and this option should be used with caution. This option is probably
466 better suited to experimental rather than natural conditions.

467 3.5.3 Pressure change

468 The “pressure change” option models the evolution of a COH fluid at equilibrium undergoing
469 isothermal pressure changes. The model is iterative. At each pressure step (every 0.01 GPa),
470 the thermodynamic parameters of the COH system are calculated. If graphite/diamond is
471 dissolved/precipitated, its isotopic composition is calculated.

472 3.5.4 Temperature change

473 The “temperature change” option models the evolution of an equilibrium COH fluid
474 undergoing isobaric thermal changes. The model is iterative. At each temperature (every 1
475 °C), the thermodynamic parameters of the COH system are calculated. In the event of
476 graphite/diamond is dissolved/precipitated, its isotopic composition is calculated.

477

478 4 Limitations

479 Maximum temperature and pressure:

480 The equation of state Thermotopes-COH software limits the applicable pressure-temperature
481 range to crustal and upper mantle geological conditions and may react poorly in eclogitic or
482 granulitic conditions. Thermodynamic equations from Huizenga, (2005) cover the range
483 above 300°C and 0.1 GPa. Pairs of P-T values in proximity of the extremes of the allowed range
484 may lead to unexpected results or errors.

485 Pure CO₂ or CH₄ fluid

486 At temperatures higher than ≈ 850 °C, the composition of carbon saturated fluids tends
487 towards pure CO₂ and CH₄ becomes virtually absent. Conversely, should the user force
488 overwhelmingly reduced conditions featuring only pure CH₄ fluid, the COH system will be left
489 to the CH system. In the endmember situations, mathematical errors may arise from ratios
490 leading to division by zero. In this event, the software will inform the user that the modeling
491 cannot be pursued due to fluid being pure CO₂ or CH₄.

492 Graphite/diamond precipitation

493 Graphite/diamond precipitation is based on Equation (23) (see Section 2.7) as the sole
494 precipitation reaction. More reactions could be considered, as the model strays from reality
495 when only CO₂ or CH₄ remains present in the fluid, such as equation (21) involving oxidation
496 of graphite/diamond in CO₂.

497

498 5 Acknowledgment

499 Isotopic parameters come mainly from a compilation of isotopic fractionation equations from
500 “IsoFrac” Jordi Delgado Martin. This work is part of a project funded by the European
501 Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation
502 program (Grant agreement No. 864045; project acronym DeepSeep). A Richard Lounsbery
503 grant and a MIUR Rita Levi Montalcini grant to AVB are also acknowledged.

504 6 Computer code availability

505 The Thermotopes-COH software was developed by Antoine Boutier, (Dipartimento di Scienze
506 della Terra, Università degli Studi di Torino, Via Valperga Caluso 35, 10100 Torino
507 antoine.boutier@gmail.com, +33-644255635), under the supervision of Alberto Vitale
508 Brovarone (Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche e Ambientali, Università di
509 Bologna, Piazza di Porta San Donato 1, 40126 Bologna; alberto.vitaleb@unibo.it). The source
510 codes and user manual are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/8364254> under an open
511 source license. The software is compatible with current Microsoft operating system Windows
512 10, and Apple Mac operating system (tested on Mojave and Catalina), and is written in
513 Python, using Python 3.7.2. The software code makes use of the freely available package

514 Matplotlib, Tkinter and Pandas, and has been compiled using Pyinstaller with Windows

515 PowerShell.

516

517 7 References

- 518 Ballhaus, C., Berry, R.F., Green, D.H., 1991. High pressure experimental calibration of the olivine-
519 orthopyroxene-spinel oxygen geobarometer: implications for the oxidation state of the
520 upper mantle. *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* 107, 27–40.
- 521 Baumgartner, L.P., Valley, J.W., 2001. Stable isotope transport and contact metamorphic fluid flow.
522 *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.* 43, 415–467.
- 523 Beaudoin, G., Therrien, P., 2009. The updated web stable isotope fractionation calculator. *Handb.*
524 *Stable Isot. Anal. Tech.* 2, 1120–1122.
- 525 Bebout, G.E., Fogel, M.L., 1992. Nitrogen-isotope compositions of metasedimentary rocks in the
526 Catalina Schist, California: implications for metamorphic devolatilization history. *Geochim.*
527 *Cosmochim. Acta* 56, 2839–2849.
- 528 Berner, R.A., 1999. A new look at the long-term carbon cycle. *Gsa Today* 9, 1–6.
- 529 Boutier, A., Martinez, I., Sissmann, O., Agostini, S., Daniel, I., Van Baalen, M., Mana, S. and
530 Brovarone, A.V., 2023. Complexity of graphite formation in response to metamorphic
531 methane generation and transformation in an orogenic ultramafic body. *Geochimica et*
532 *Cosmochimica Acta*.
- 533 Cesare, B., 1995. Graphite precipitation in C—O—H fluid inclusions: closed system compositional and
534 density changes, and thermobarometric implications. *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* 122, 25–33.
- 535 Connolly, J.A.D., 1995. Phase diagram methods for graphitic rocks and application to the system C-
536 O- H- FeO- TiO₂- SiO₂. *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* 119, 94–116.
- 537 Connolly, J.A.D., Cesare, B., 1993. C-O-H-S fluid composition and oxygen fugacity in graphitic
538 metapelites. *J. Metamorph. Geol.* 11, 379–388.
- 539 Dansgaard, W., 1964. Stable isotopes in precipitation. *Tellus* 16, 436–468.
- 540 Dasgupta, R., 2013. Ingassing, Storage, and Outgassing of Terrestrial Carbon through Geologic Time.
541 *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.* 75, 183–229. <https://doi.org/10.2138/rmg.2013.75.7>
- 542 Dasgupta, R., Hirschmann, M.M., 2010. The deep carbon cycle and melting in Earth's interior. *Earth*
543 *Planet. Sci. Lett.* 298, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2010.06.039>
- 544 Day, H.W., 2012. A revised diamond-graphite transition curve. *Am. Mineral.* 97, 52–62.
- 545 de Santis, R., Breedveld, G.J.F., Prausnitz, J.M., 1974. Thermodynamic properties of aqueous gas
546 mixtures at advanced pressures. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Process Des. Dev.* 13, 374–377.
- 547 Duke, E.F., Rumble, D., 1986. Textural and isotopic variations in graphite from plutonic rocks, south-
548 central New Hampshire. *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* 93, 409–419.
- 549 Evans, K., 2011. Metamorphic carbon fluxes: how much and how fast? *Geology* 39, 95–96.
- 550 French, B.M., 1966. Some geological implications of equilibrium between graphite and a C-H-O gas
551 phase at high temperatures and pressures. *Rev. Geophys.* 4, 223–253.
- 552 Frost, B.R., 2018. Introduction to oxygen fugacity and its petrologic importance, in: *Oxide Minerals.*
553 *De Gruyter*, pp. 1–10.
- 554 Galvez, M.E., Beyssac, O., Martinez, I., Benzerara, K., Chaduteau, C., Malvoisin, B. and Malavieille, J.,
555 2013. Graphite formation by carbonate reduction during subduction. *Nature Geoscience*,
556 6(6), pp.473-477.
- 557 Holloway, J.R., 1984. Graphite-CH₄-H₂O-CO₂ equilibria at low-grade metamorphic conditions.
558 *Geology* 12, 455–458.
- 559 Holloway, J.R., 1977. Fugacity and activity of molecular species in supercritical fluids, in:
560 *Thermodynamics in Geology.* Springer, pp. 161–181.
- 561 Huang, F., Daniel, I., Cardon, H., Montagnac, G., Sverjensky, D.A., 2017. Immiscible hydrocarbon
562 fluids in the deep carbon cycle. *Nat. Commun.* 8, 1–8.
- 563 Huizenga, J.M., 2005. COH, an Excel spreadsheet for composition calculations in the COH fluid
564 system. *Comput. Geosci.* 31, 797–800.
- 565 Kendall, C., McDonnell, J.J., 2012. *Isotope tracers in catchment hydrology.* Elsevier Science
566 Publishers: Amsterdam.

567 Kitchen, N.E., Valley, J.W., 1995. Carbon isotope thermometry in marbles of the Adirondack
568 Mountains, New York. *J. Metamorph. Geol.* 13, 577–594.

569 Kokh, M.A., Akinfiev, N.N., Pokrovski, G.S., Salvi, S., Guillaume, D., 2017. The role of carbon dioxide in
570 the transport and fractionation of metals by geological fluids. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*
571 197, 433–466.

572 Luque, F.J., Crespo-Feo, E., Barrenechea, J.F., Ortega, L., 2012. Carbon isotopes of graphite:
573 Implications on fluid history. *Geosci. Front.* 3, 197–207.

574 Mason, E., Edmonds, M., Turchyn, A.V., 2017. Remobilization of crustal carbon may dominate
575 volcanic arc emissions. *Science* 357, 290–294.

576 Miozzi, F., Tumiatì, S., 2020. Aqueous concentration of CO₂ in carbon-saturated fluids as a highly
577 sensitive oxybarometer. *Geochem Persp Lett* 16, 30–34.

578 Ohmoto, H., Kerrick, D.M., 1977. Devolatilization equilibria in graphitic systems. *Am. J. Sci.* 277,
579 1013–1044.

580 Ortega, L., Millward, D., Luque, F.J., Barrenechea, J.F., Beyssac, O., Huizenga, J.-M., Rodas, M., Clarke,
581 S.M., 2010. The graphite deposit at Borrowdale (UK): a catastrophic mineralizing event
582 associated with Ordovician magmatism. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 74, 2429–2449.

583 Ray, J.S., 2009. Carbon isotopic variations in fluid-deposited graphite: evidence for multicomponent
584 Rayleigh isotopic fractionation. *Int. Geol. Rev.* 51, 45–57.

585 Ray, J.S., Ramesh, R., 2000. Rayleigh fractionation of stable isotopes from a multicomponent source.
586 *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 64, 299–306.

587 Rayleigh, Lord, 1896. L. Theoretical considerations respecting the separation of gases by diffusion
588 and similar processes. *Lond. Edinb. Dublin Philos. Mag. J. Sci.* 42, 493–498.

589 Richet, P., Bottinga, Y., & Javoy, M., 1977. A review of hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen, oxygen, sulphur,
590 and chlorine stable isotope fractionation among gaseous molecules. *Annual Review of Earth*
591 *and Planetary Sciences*, 5(1), 65-110.

592 Rumble, D. and Hoering, T.C., 1986. Carbon isotope geochemistry of graphite vein deposits from
593 New Hampshire, USA. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 50(6), 1239-1247.

594 Sharp, Z., 2017. Principles of Stable Isotope Geochemistry, 2nd Edition. Pearson Prentice Hall.
595 <https://doi.org/10.25844/h9q1-0p82>

596 Shi, P., Saxena, S.K., 1992. Thermodynamic modeling of the CHOS fluid system. *Am. Mineral.* 77,
597 1038–1049.

598 Spycher, N.F., Reed, M.H., 1988. Fugacity coefficients of H₂, CO₂, CH₄, H₂O and of H₂O- CO₂-CH₄
599 mixtures: A virial equation treatment for moderate pressures and temperatures applicable
600 to calculations of hydrothermal boiling. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 52, 739–749.
601 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037\(88\)90334-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-7037(88)90334-1)

602 Stachel, T., Chacko, T., Luth, R.W., 2017. Carbon isotope fractionation during diamond growth in
603 depleted peridotite: Counterintuitive insights from modelling water-maximum CHO fluids as
604 multi-component systems. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 473, 44–51.

605 Stagno, V., Frost, D.J., 2010. Carbon speciation in the asthenosphere: Experimental measurements of
606 the redox conditions at which carbonate-bearing melts coexist with graphite or diamond in
607 peridotite assemblages. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 300, 72–84.

608 Taylor, B.E., Liou, J.G., 1978. The low-temperature stability of andradite in COH fluids. *Am. Mineral.*
609 63, 378–393.

610 Taylor, W.R., Green, D.H., 1986. The role of reduced COH fluids in mantle partial melting, in:
611 International Kimberlite Conference: Extended Abstracts. pp. 211–213.

612 Tumiatì, S., Recchia, S., Remusat, L., Tiraboschi, C., Sverjensky, D.A., Manning, C.E., Vitale Brovarone,
613 A., Boutier, A., Spanu, D., Poli, S., 2022. Subducted organic matter buffered by marine
614 carbonate rules the carbon isotopic signature of arc emissions. *Nat. Commun.* 13, 1–10.

615 Tumiatì, S., Tiraboschi, C., Miozzi, F., Vitale-Brovarone, A., Manning, C.E., Sverjensky, D.A., Milani, S.,
616 Poli, S., 2020. Dissolution susceptibility of glass-like carbon versus crystalline graphite in

617 high-pressure aqueous fluids and implications for the behavior of organic matter in
618 subduction zones. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 273, 383–402.
619 Ulmer, P., Luth, R.W., 1991. The graphite-COH fluid equilibrium in P, T, f_{O_2} space.
620 *Contrib. Mineral. Petrol.* 106, 265–272.
621 Valley, J.W., 1986. Stable isotope geochemistry of metamorphic rocks. *Rev. Mineral. Geochem.* 16,
622 445–489.
623 Valley, J.W., O’Neil, J.R., 1981. $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ exchange between calcite and graphite: a possible
624 thermometer in Grenville marbles. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 45, 411–419.
625 Vitale Brovarone, A., Tumiati, S., Piccoli, F., Ague, J.J., Connolly, J.A., Beyssac, O., 2020. Fluid-
626 mediated selective dissolution of subducting carbonaceous material: Implications for carbon
627 recycling and fluid fluxes at forearc depths. *Chem. Geol.* 549, 119682.
628

629 8 Supplementary material

630 **Supplementary material 1:**

631 The multicomponent model featured in tab 3 allows to monitor the isotopic evolution of a
632 fluid containing both CO_2 and CH_4 in the case of precipitation of graphite/diamond. However,
633 it does consider neither the mechanism, nor the thermodynamic settings linked to the
634 precipitation. The Dissolution/precipitation model presented in tab 5 aims at coupling
635 thermodynamic and isotopic evolutions. Here is a comparison of results provided by both
636 methods from the modeling of desiccation of a fluid at $\text{CH}_4/\text{CO}_2=0.9$ at 800°C and 4 GPa (in
637 the diamond stability field) from a fluid with an initial $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ composition of 0 ‰.
638 Supplementary Figure 1 shows the results for each model, which are in excellent agreement

639 with each other. However, these methods can only be compared by desiccation process as
640 this is the only process supported by the multicomponent model.

641 Supplementary figure 1: Comparison of the diamond and fluid in the Thermotopes-COH
642 (TCOH) tab 5 Dissolution/precipitation and from the multicomponent system (MC). A:
643 Evolution of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of diamond and fluid for each system as a function of the $\text{CO}_2/(\text{CO}_2+\text{CH}_4)$
644 ratio. B: Evolution of the Δ diamond-fluid for each system as a function of the $\text{CO}_2/(\text{CO}_2+\text{CH}_4)$
645 ratio.

